

Limited cross-modal activation to visual language in the auditory cortices of hearing-impaired children

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ABSTRACT

What predicts spoken language outcomes in hearing-impaired children has been insufficiently understood, particularly with respect to cross-modal neural activation and sign language input. This study assessed neural activation in the auditory cortices of Czech-learning preschoolers with cochlear implants (CI), hearing aids (HA), and normal-hearing (NH) controls. The children were exposed to auditory speech, visual silent speech, and sign language, while hemodynamic activity was recorded using fNIRS. In response to auditory speech, CI children had weaker cortical activation than both NH and HA children. Rather surprisingly, sign language yielded reliable activation in the right auditory cortex of normal-hearing children, arguably reflecting the processing of the regular, relatively slow, sign language rhythm patterns. Visual silent speech failed to elicit reliable hemodynamic activation in hearing-impaired children, but yielded a non-significant trend in CI children left-laterally. Inverted hemodynamic responses were observed for silent speech in HA and NH children, possibly indicating auditory suppression during speech imagery. Experience with sign language modulated auditory speech processing: CI children with prior sign language input exhibited reliable cortical activation to auditory speech (unlike CI children without sign language input), suggesting a scaffolding effect of early experience with sign language on the development of spoken language. The findings advance the current understanding of how auditory and visual language processing develop in children with hearing loss, and highlight the cross-modal contributions of sensory experience and early language exposure.

1. Introduction

Language acquisition in typically developing children relies heavily on the auditory modality, particularly during the earliest stages of a child's language development. However, approximately one to three infants per 1000 live births are affected by congenital hearing loss (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2010) and do not thus have early access to auditory speech input. Around 14 to 32% of pediatric hearing losses are developed postnatally (Duan et al., 2022). While many prelingually deaf children receive medically restored hearing and eventually have access to spoken language input, there is considerable variation in the level of communicative competence they achieve (Pisoni et al., 2018; Tamati et al., 2022). It has been proposed that spoken

language acquisition in prelingually deaf children is influenced by cross-modal activation across the visual and auditory cortices (Mushtaq et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2005; Campbell and Sharma, 2016), but it remains unclear how. The present study investigates cross-modal cortical activation in prelingually deaf and normal-hearing children, and explores its relation to auditory and linguistic measures. Existing studies attempting to unravel the sources that contribute to the hearing-impaired children's highly variable language outcomes have rarely produced conclusive results. Factors describing general hearing experience, such as age of hearing loss, severity of hearing loss (Birman and Sanli, 2020), age at hearing device fitting (Nicholas and Geers, 2007; Farag et al., 2024) as well as external aspects, such as socioeconomic status (Lee et al., 2025), parental behaviours (Lin et al., 2025),

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rehabilitation and communication mode (Geers et al., 2002) and sign language exposure (Delcenserie et al., 2024) are often reported as significant, but they do not explain all the variability.

Besides the modulating factors that stem from the child's environment, hearing diagnosis and type of compensation, the literature has highlighted the contribution of various neurocognitive factors, in particular neural plasticity and cross-modal cortical organisation. Sensory experience modulates the structural and functional organisation of the brain throughout lifetime (Rubic, 2020), and in the early stages of one's life, it determines the development of brain structures. In case of prolonged sensory deprivation, the lack of interaction between the primary auditory cortex and higher-order auditory cortices may cause functional decoupling, which may later interfere with hearing restoration (Kral et al., 2005; Kral, 2007). When no corresponding sensory input is provided, the cortical structures are able to readapt and become responsive to stimuli presented in a different modality, as documented by many studies with deaf and blind individuals (reviewed for example by Vinogradova and Cardin, 2024).

The auditory cortices of hearing-impaired individuals often become responsive to visual stimulation with and without linguistic content. For example, when observing moving dots deaf adults show activity in the right auditory cortex (larger activity than in hearing controls), which suggests engagement of this area in visual motion processing (Finney et al. 2001, Dewey and Hartley 2015). Prelingually deaf adults have also been shown to employ the secondary auditory cortex during the comprehension of a nonverbal animated movie (Zimmermann et al. 2024) and to employ the primary and secondary auditory cortices in task switching (Manini et al. 2022).

The auditory cortex is activated also in response to visual linguistic stimuli in deaf users of sign language (Nishimura et al., 1999; Nishimura et al., 2000; Petitto et al., 2000; MacSweeney et al., 2008; Lambertz et al., 2005), in a similar way as it is activated by spoken language in hearing individuals (Sakai et al. 2005).

The neural activation of the left temporal auditory cortices in response to sign language is in Deaf signers reportedly even stronger than it is in hearing native signers (MacSweeney et al. 2002), and the level of the activation seems to be related to the degree of hearing loss (Lambertz et al. 2005). Non-sign movements, too, seem to elicit activation in the auditory cortices of deaf signers, suggesting that familiarity with the visual modality alone is sufficient to engage these brain regions, even in the absence of semantic content (Petitto et al., 2000). The discovery of the brain's ability to repurpose the auditory areas for processing visual (language) stimuli led to the proposal of the so-called "visual takeover theory". Advocates of this theory warned against signing with young children who were about to get fitted with auditory prostheses. One of the strongest claims even shows concern that sign language exposure might cause irreversible damages: "Exposure to sign language in the first three years of life locks the language system into a vision-only configuration that prevents possible future acquisition of auditory language" (Giraud and Lee, 2007, p. 382). This statement was supported by a handful of studies that found correlations between greater activation in the auditory area by visual stimuli and poorer performance in speech perception (Lee et al., 2001; Lee et al., 2005, Buckley and Tobey, 2011, Sandmann et al., 2012; Zhou et al., 2018).

Findings of more recent studies, however, reveal a completely different picture, showing that the cross-modal reorganisation of the auditory areas for processing visual language stimuli has compensatory benefits and may even be adaptive for the development of spoken communication when hearing is restored (studies with children: Mush-taq et al., 2020, Zhou et al., 2023; studies with adults: Anderson et al., 2017a; Paul et al., 2022). The facilitative role of cross-modal activation might be related to findings that early sign language exposure benefits the development of spoken language in children with compensated hearing loss (Davidson et al., 2014; Pontecorvo et al., 2023; Delcenserie et al., 2024). Cross-modal activation is also associated with advanced lipreading abilities, which are crucial for communicative success in

difficult listening situations (Calvert et al., 1997). Bergeson et al. (2005) reported that pediatric patients who had enhanced pre-implantation lipreading abilities had superior performance in speech perception, speech intelligibility, and language skills three years post implantation, compared to patients with poor pre-implantation lipreading abilities. Lalonde and McCreery (2020) showed that children with hearing loss benefited from visual cues more than children with normal hearing in sentence recognition task under difficult listening conditions.

What are the mechanisms that allow spoken language to benefit from early exposure to visual language? The literature has argued that stronger activation in the temporal cortex in response to visual speech may reflect stronger associations between the two modalities (Anderson et al. 2017b). In line with that proposal, recent findings show positive correlation between the auditory-visual area connectivity and comprehension in noise in hearing-impaired adults (Fullerton et al. 2023). Many aspects of experience-driven cross-modal plasticity are still insufficiently understood, and developmental research in particular is virtually lacking. Most previous work has focused on adults or adolescents, often with widely varying age ranges. To our knowledge, no studies have examined cross-modal activation in preschool and early school-age children. The lack of studies is attributable to deaf preschoolers being a particularly vulnerable population, which is difficult to reach on one hand, and rather challenging to run experiments with, on the other. This study aims to assess cross-modal activation precisely in this age group as preschool and early school age are crucial for spoken language development, which scaffolds school-based learning, reading, writing, and later academic and professional achievement in general (Hohm et al., 2007, Jago et al., 2025)

As prior research indicated that both sign language exposure and lipreading abilities are positively related to spoken language outcomes and comprehension, we set out to test cross-modal activation in both these types of visual language cues. To provide a comprehensive picture of language-related cross-modal activation, we measured neural activation in children's auditory cortices in response to sign language, silent speech (i.e. visual speech), and auditory speech. Hemodynamic cortical activation was measured in the temporal region, including the superior temporal gyrus and adjacent areas, which are regions typically associated with auditory speech processing. We assessed three groups of preschool/early school aged children differing in their hearing experience: prelingually deaf children with cochlear implants, prelingually deaf children with hearing aids, and age-matched normal-hearing controls. Our first goal was to reveal whether there is cross-modal activation to silent speech and/or sign language in the hearing-impaired children. We hypothesized that compared to children with normal hearing, children with cochlear implants and children with hearing aids would exhibit stronger activation in conditions not involving sound (visual speech and sign language). Based on prior research with adults with different degrees of hearing loss, one can expect that cross-modal activation to sign language would be strongest to the children with cochlear implants, who have a more severe hearing loss than the children with hearing aids. In the auditory speech condition, we predicted to find strong activation in children with normal hearing and attenuated response patterns in children with hearing aids and children with cochlear implants.

The second goal was to explore whether the processing of language (auditory or visual) is modulated by specific auditory and linguistic factors, thus aiming to shed more light on the frequently observed variation in language outcomes of hearing-impaired children. We tested the effects of hearing age, pure tone aided audiometry, vocabulary size, and prior sign language input. Intuitively, one would predict greater cortical activation in children with higher hearing age and/or greater hearing benefits from the device. Greater activation in the sign language condition might also be associated with the amount of sign language/signing exposure. Along similar lines, greater activation in the auditory speech condition might be associated with vocabulary score. However, as these are rather intuitive predictions, without strong support in the

sparse prior literature, the analysis of the modulating factors should be considered exploratory.

2. Method

2.1. Participants

A total of 38 children with normal hearing and 28 children with diagnosed hearing loss participated in the study, out of whom 10 children were fitted hearing aids (HAs) and 18 were implanted with cochlear implants (CIs). Four CI children were removed from the analysis based on epoch rejection (described below), as they had fewer than two usable epochs in at least one condition. One child from the HA group was excluded due to having more than 25% of channels marked as bad, which exceeded our predefined cutoff.

The final, analysed, sample included 14 children with CIs (8 females, 6 males; mean age: 69 months, all but two children had hearing parents; all children with CIs had been fitted with HAs before implantation), 9 children with HAs (6 females, 3 males; mean age: 85 months, all with hearing parents), and 38 children with normal hearing (22 females, 16 males; mean age: 63 months, all raised monolingually by Czech-speaking parents). Sign language exposure was assessed via parental report on a scale from 0 to 5, where 0 = no use, 1 = exceptional use of isolated signs, 2 = selected isolated signs, 3 = signing in 25-50% of interactions, 4 = signing in 25-75% of interactions, 5 = 75-100% (though value 5 was not reported by any of the parents). Spoken language was the primary communication mode for all children. For analysis, these parent-reported values were transformed into a binary categorical variable with the levels “without systematic exposure to sign language”, corresponding to parent-reported values 0, 1, and 2, and “with systematic exposure to sign language”, corresponding to parent-reported values 3, 4, and 5. The characteristics of the hearing-impaired children in the analysed dataset are presented in [Tables 1](#) and [2](#).

Children with typical development and normal hearing were

recruited from our babylab database. Children with hearing loss were tested either at the the University Hospital in Hradec Králové or in a quiet room at the SUKI summer camp venue; normal-hearing children were tested in the psycholinguistics lab at Charles University in Prague. The inclusion criteria for both the clinical and control groups were: age between two and nine years, no reported cognitive or motor disorders, ability to cooperate, and normal or corrected-to-normal vision. All the children were learning Czech, and many of the deaf children were also exposed to Czech Sign Language (to varying extent); Czech and Czech Sign Language were thus the two languages employed in our stimuli.

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University Hospital Hradec Králové, and the protocol adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki. All participants' parents were informed about the procedure and purpose of the study and provided their consent by signing an informed consent form. Children with hearing loss were contacted through the University Hospital Hradec Králové and the Czech Association of Cochlear Implant Users (SUKI).

2.2. Stimuli and procedure

Participants were tested individually in one session. The session consisted of a neuroimaging fNIRS experiment, followed by behavioral language assessment tasks. The stimuli for the fNIRS experiment consisted of short stories specifically created for this study by the first author. A total of 18 stories were used, with six stories per condition; all children saw the same six stories in the same condition. Importantly, all stories were similar in vocabulary complexity, and all were recorded in a child-directed manner to minimize differences in emotional or arousal content. A native Czech speaker (female), who was also a Czech Sign Language (CSL) interpreter, was recorded telling the stories in both Czech and CSL. The duration of the stimuli ranged from 30 to 41 seconds, with no significant differences in duration between the conditions. Post-processing was applied to the recorded audio-video materials as follows. In the auditory speech condition, a beige splotch was applied

Table 1
Characteristics of children with cochlear implants included in the analysis.

ID	Sex	Age (m)	Better ear PTA [dB]	Etiology	Implant	CI type	Aided PTA (dB)	First HAs (age in m)	First CI (age in m)	Hearing age with CI (m)	Sign input	Vocab score
HI_001	F	64	120	meningitis	bilateral	N7 Nucleus	38.8	4	12	52	3	25
HI_003	F	47	100	non-syndromic genetic	bilateral	synch NA	NA	20	28	19	4	NA
HI_004	F	52	87.5	syncl. Waardengurg	bilateral	N7 Nucleus	31.3	24	32	20	2	11
HI_006	F	68	97.5	Wolfram-like syndrom	bilateral	synch Rondo3	42.5	29	64	3	3	11
HI_007	F	71	120	non-GJB2 non-syndromic	bilateral	synch Q90	32.5	26	35	36	3	NA
HI_008	M	34	100	GJB2 mutation	bilateral	synch N7	NA	3	11	23	2	NA
HI_009	M	64	86	GJB2 mutation	bilateral	synch N7 Nucleus	41.3	7	21	43	4	28
HI_014	M	91	120	non-GJB2 nonsyndr.. genetic	bilateral	synch Rondo3	NA	3	12	60	3	NA
HI_015	F	63	105	non-syndromic genetic	bilatetal	synch Rondo3	35	29	38	26	4	20
HI_016	F	65	100	syndrome Pendred	bilatetal	synch N7 Nucleus	32.5	12	24	40	3	15
HI_017	M	93	50	GJB2 mutation	bilatetal	synch N7 Nucleus	32,5	5	15	78	1	40
HI_018	M	65	120	GJB2 mutation	unilat. (L) + HA	synch N7 Nucleus	35	5	19	46	3	26
HI_019	M	98	75	NA	bilateral	metach Q90	20	8	66	32	0	NA
HI_028	F	93	96,25	GJB2 mutation	bilateral	synch Kanso	23,75	3	14	79	1	35
Mean		69.1	98.1				33.2	12.7	27.9	39.8	2.6	23.4
SD		18.8	19.8				6.8	10.5	18.0	2.,1	1.2	10.2

Table 2
Characteristics of children with hearing aids included in the analysis.

ID	Sex	Age (m)	Better ear PTA [dB]	Etiology	HA type	Aided PTA [dB]	First HAs (m)	Hearing age (m)	Sign input	Vocab score
HI_005	F	73	35	syndrome	Phonak Sky	20	63	10	0	30
HI_012	F	66	20	Waardenburg idiopathic	PHONAK SKY B70-SP	NA	14	52	0	26
HI_020	M	81	77.5	X-linked non-syndromic idiopathic	PHONAK SKY M70-SP	43.8	32	49	2	35
KI_021	M	86	52.5	idiopathic	PHONAK SKY M50-PR	31.3	58	29	0	33
HI_022	F	73	33.8	idiopathic	PHONAK SKY M70-PR	30	12	61	1	31
HI_024	F	105	47.5	GJB2 mutation	Sky Q50-M13 H2O	25	7	98	1	35
HI_025	M	95	55	idiopathic	Sky V30-M P SP UP	17.5	5	90	1	35
HI_026	F	96	15	idiopathic	NA	NA	40	56	0	39
HI_027	F	86	43.8	idiopathic	PHONAK SKY M70-M	36.3	46	41	0	34
Mean		84.54	42.23			29.13	30.65	53.89	0.56	33.11
SD		12.68	19.05			9.20	22.25	27.50	0.73	3.72

over the speaker’s mouth to eliminate lipreading cues thus promoting auditory cues. The Silent speech and Sign language conditions were muted.

The stimuli were presented in two blocks, with three trials per condition in each block and a short pause between the blocks. There were four versions of a pseudo-randomized order in which the stimuli were presented. Participants were instructed to pay attention and remain still during the testing. To minimize leg, hand, and other body movements, children had their feet on a footrest and were asked to hold a teddy bear, which had been shown to help minimize movement during piloting. During testing, the administrator was seated behind a barrier but could still monitor whether the child was focused.

The silent inter-trial intervals presented a fixation screen with a centrally positioned black and white cartoon drawing on a black background. Typically, a small fixation cross is used in such studies (Mushtaq et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2023; Anderson et al., 2017b); however, piloting showed that both adults and children perceived a fixation cross as irritating and the resulting annoyance interfered with their attention. This is why we instead presented more attractive, yet simple, black and white pictures during the inter-trial rest periods. The rest periods lasted between 25 and 28 seconds. Fig. 1 illustrates the experimental design.

After the neuroimaging part of the session and a short rest, the child

completed a standardized Czech language vocabulary test (Seidlová Málková and Smolík, 2014). The test consisted of 40 items in total, and each item was scored with one point, yielding a maximum possible score of 40. The plan was to also administer a standardized grammatical test; however, this turned out to be a rather demanding final task for most of the children and was therefore excluded. Prior to the experiment, almost all children had undergone a pure tone audiometry test with the compensation device, based on which we report the pure tone average value in dB (i.e. the severity of hearing loss) for the less impaired ear.

2.3. Material and equipment

The experiment was implemented in PsychoPy (Peirce et al., 2019). Hemodynamic data were collected using the NIRSport2 device (by NIRx Medizintechnik GmbH) at wavelengths of 760 and 850 nm, using the acquisition software Aurora on an HP Pavilion laptop.

The optode setup consisted of 8 sources and 7 detectors (plus 8 short-distance detectors for movement-artifacts correction), resulting in a montage with 9 and 8 channels on the left and right hemisphere, respectively, as shown in Fig. 2. The probe arrangement was based on the LONI atlas (with STG specificity of 30%), as applied in the FOLD software (Zimeo Morais et al., 2018). All probes were inserted into a

Fig. 1. Trial types and experimental design of the present study.

Fig. 2. The montage used in the experiment, based on the LONI atlas. The top-most detector on the right hemisphere (shown as a dashed circle, location of F10) was occupied by a bundle of short-distance detectors. In the statistical analyses, channel 0L was not analyzed to keep the hemispheric symmetry.

fitting child-sized EasyCap.

The stimuli were presented on a 24-inch computer screen placed approximately 75 cm away in front of the child. The screen's height was individually adjusted to ensure that the child would not tilt their head back. Auditory stimuli were presented through two loudspeakers placed at 30-degree angles frontally, at a distance of about 1 meter from the child. The SPL level measured at the child's location was 65 dB in the normal hearing group and 75 dB in the children with hearing loss.

Our methodological decision to increase the sound level from 65 dB SPL to 75 dB SPL limits the comparability of the groups in the auditory condition. We made this adjustment deliberately because we were concerned that insufficient audibility might reduce attention and experiment completion in the hearing-impaired children. At the same time, the sound level was not adjusted on an individual basis (which would have been the preferred approach), as PTA thresholds were not available for all children and collecting them within the experimental session would prolong the, already rather long, testing time.

2.4. Data preprocessing and analysis

The fNIRS data were processed using the MNE-Python library (Gramfort et al., 2013) and the MNE-NIRS extension (Luke et al., 2021). First, the raw data were converted to optical density (OD). Short-channel regression was performed to reduce systemic responses originating in the extracerebral tissue and to separate physiological signals from the neural responses (Wyser et al., 2020). The MNE-NIRS function we used was Systemic correction regression based on the nearest channel adopted from Luke et al. (2021); the method is based on previous work of Fabbri et al. (2004), Saager and Berger (2005), and Scholkmann et al. (2014). Scalp Coupling Index (SCI) was used to detect bad channels. Channels with $SCI < 0.75$ were marked as bad and interpolated; this threshold was adopted from Pollonini et al. (2014). After applying this approach, out of the 61 participants, one participant

had more than 4 bad channels (i.e. $> 25\%$) and was excluded from further analysis; three participants had two bad channels and three other participants had four bad channels, which were interpolated, and these participants' data were further analysed.

The optical density data were transformed to hemoglobin concentrations using the Beer-Lambert Law ($DPF = 5.25$). Data were band-pass filtered between 0.01 Hz and 0.5 Hz to remove high frequency noise (e. g. heart beat); the filter cutoff values were chosen based on previous studies with similar design and populations (Zhou et al., 2023; Anderson et al., 2017a; Anderson et al., 2019) while choosing such lower cutoff that does not filter out our stimulation frequency (maximum stimulation time plus maximum silence duration were 41 s and 28 s, respectively, thus yielding the lowest possible stimulation frequency of $1/69 = 0.014$ Hz). To further reduce noise in the data caused by participants' head motion, the negative enhancement correlation algorithm was applied to the filtered data. This approach assumes that oxyhemoglobin and deoxyhemoglobin concentration changes following neural activity are strongly negatively correlated, and that the relationship is opposite if concentration changes are caused by head movements (Cui et al., 2010).

The data were segmented into epochs defined between -5 s and 40 s relative to the onset of stimulation. Baseline correction was applied relative to the interval -5–0 s before stimulus onset. Epochs were rejected if the maximum peak-to-peak amplitude exceeded 4 μM . Only those participants who had at least 2 epochs in each condition were retained for further analysis. Table 3 presents the mean number of

Table 3

Mean number of remaining epochs by group and condition; means and standard deviations in brackets.

Group	Silent	Sign	Audio
NH	5.03 (1.28)	5.11 (1.25)	5.26 (1.08)
HA	5.44 (0.527)	5.11 (1.05)	4.67 (1.12)
CI	4.79 (1.25)	5.21 (1.12)	5.21 (0.975)

remaining epochs for each group and condition. The data were averaged across all the remaining epochs for each participant. Following prior literature, HbO values were chosen as indicators of neural activity (Quaresima and Ferrari, 2019). We calculated the average HbO change within the time window between 5 s and 20 s after stimulus onset.

2.5. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was done in R (R core team, 2020) using the lme4 and lmerTest packages (Bates et al., 2015; Kuznetsova et al., 2017), the emmeans (Lenth and Piaskowski, 2025) package for pairwise comparisons, the ggeffects package for calculating modelled means and confidence intervals (Lüdtke, 2018), and ggplot2 for visualisation (Wickham, 2016).

The HbO values were first submitted to an omnibus model to identify the channels with significant activation across conditions and groups. This was a linear mixed-effects model with the fixed effects of Group (NH as reference level, HA, CI), Condition (auditory speech as reference level, silent speech, sign language), Hemisphere (sum-coded left vs. right), Channel (1 vs 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8; symmetrically across the left and right hemisphere) and their interactions. The random structure modelled per-participant intercepts and slopes for Condition. In the first model, channel 6 turned out to yield the largest activation across all channels, and it was also the only channel with activation being reliably larger than 0 (see Appendix Table A1 for the full model summary). Therefore, a subsequent linear mixed-effects model fitted the HbO values measured at channels 6 (bilaterally) with the fixed effects of Group (NH as reference level, HA, CI), Condition (auditory speech as reference level, silent speech, sign language), and Hemisphere (sum-coded left vs. right), including per-participant random intercepts and random slopes for Condition.

Four other, exploratory linear mixed-effects models were fitted, again on HbO measured at channel 6 bilaterally. The first exploratory analysis modelled the effect of Hearing age (numeric, z-scored), including Group (sum-coded HA vs CI), Condition (auditory as reference level, silent, sign), and their interactions. The second exploratory analysis modelled the effects of Pure-tone gain (numeric, z-scored), Group (sum-coded HA vs CI), Condition (auditory as reference level, silent, sign), and their interactions. The third exploratory model fitted the fixed effects of Vocabulary score (numeric, z-scored), Group (sum-coded HA vs CI), Condition (audio as reference level, silent, sign), and their interaction. The fourth and final exploratory analysis modelled the effects of Sign language input (sum-coded, none vs. some), Condition (audio as reference level, silent, sign), and their interaction in CI children only (because none of the HA children had been exposed to sign language). All the exploratory models included per-participant random intercepts and random slopes for Condition. The number of participants entering each of these models varied because many participants failed to provide some of the measures (data were missing especially for the PTA thresholds and Vocabulary); the total of CI and HA children analysed in the respective models was 22 for Hearing age, 14 for Aided auditory thresholds, 19 for Vocabulary, and 14 CI children only for Sign language (since HA children did not have sign language exposure).

Note that the present sample size is relatively small, which reduces the statistical power of the statistical analyses. However, in sensitive populations such as young children with hearing loss, particularly in smaller countries, recruiting larger samples is often not feasible. Related to this, children who are deaf or hard-of-hearing (DHH) represent a highly heterogeneous population with substantial variability in their hearing and language experiences, which is also reflected in our sample.

3. Results

3.1. Identifying significant channels

Fig. 3 displays the hemodynamic response functions (HRFs) for each

channel, group, and condition. The omnibus model (whose summary is reported in Table A1 in the Appendix) showed that pooled across conditions and groups, channel 6 yielded the largest response on both hemispheres and it was channel 6 where the response was reliably larger than 0; Figure A1 in the Appendix shows the estimated mean HbO change per channel and hemisphere.

Visual inspection of the HRFs in Fig. 3 aligns with this finding. It is seen that the temporally located channels 6 (bilaterally) yield the largest HbO amplitude especially for auditory speech, across groups. Channel 6 covers the supratemporal gyrus (STG) – an area typically associated with the processing of auditory stimuli and higher order processing associated with speech perception – whose significant activation is expected in response to auditory and speech stimuli. While at the temporal channels 6, 5, and 8 for auditory speech, the HRF followed a canonical pattern, characterized by a positive peak in HbO concentration approximately 5 s to 10 s after stimulus onset and an associated decrease of HbR concentration, at many other channels and for other conditions, we observed a reversed HRF pattern, the possible origins of which we will return to in the Discussion.

3.2. Comparing activation across conditions and groups

The fixed-effects summary of the model for HbO measured at channel 6 is shown in Table 4. The estimated means and 95% confidence intervals per Group, Condition, and Hemisphere are shown in Fig. 4.

The significant intercept in Table 4 shows that activation to Auditory speech in NH children was significant, estimated at 0.456 μM . The significant effects of Condition indicate that activation to Sign language and to Silent speech was in the NH children smaller than their activation to Auditory speech (by on average 0.348 μM and 0.427 μM , respectively). The significant main effect of Group means that activation to Auditory speech in CI children was smaller than in NH children (by on average 0.362 μM). The significant interactions of Condition and Group suggests that the difference in activation relative to Auditory speech, was for Sign language and Silent speech smaller in CI children than in NH children. Inspection of the estimated 95% confidence intervals in Fig. 5 further shows that on the right hemisphere, besides Auditory speech, NH children also had reliable activation to Silent speech and Sign language ($p < 0.05$). On the left hemisphere, CI children had activation to Silent speech which just missed the significance level of 0.05 (since the estimated 95% confidence interval just contains 0).

Taken together, these results demonstrate activation to visual language stimuli (silent speech and sign language) in a channel that, at the same time, strongly responds to auditory speech stimuli (and lies in the cortical region, STG, typically associated with auditory speech processing). This provides evidence of cross-modal activation, right-laterally in NH children to both silent speech and sign language, and a (near-significant) trend of cross-modal activation left-laterally in CI children to silent speech.

3.3. Exploratory analyses of audiometric and linguistic factors in hearing-impaired children

Fixed-effect summaries of the four exploratory models are shown in Tables A2 through A5 in the Appendix. The first exploratory model did not detect any significant effects involving Hearing age. The second exploratory model showed a significant main effect of Aided auditory thresholds as well as an interaction with Condition. The estimate for the main effect was +0.138 μM , which indicates larger activation to auditory speech with larger Aided pure-tone audiometry thresholds (PTA), i. e. with worse hearing. The direction of this effect is surprising, as stronger activation would be expected with lower PTA scores; however, as PTA values were available for only 14 children across both groups, these findings should be interpreted with caution. The estimated means per Group and Condition in interaction with Hearing age and Aided auditory thresholds are plotted in panels A and B of Fig. 6, respectively.

Fig. 3. Grand averages of hemodynamic responses across all channels for all groups and conditions. Note the different range of the y-axis it the graphs for CI children.

Table 4
Fixed-effects model summary for HbO on channel 6 bilaterally.

Fixed Effects	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept = ConditionAuditory, groupNH)	0.456	0.053	60.157	8.561	<0.001
ConditionSign	-0.348	0.065	59.191	-5.378	<0.001
ConditionSilent	-0.427	0.064	61.821	-6.626	<0.001
groupHA	0.017	0.121	58.545	0.139	0.890
groupCI	-0.362	0.102	58.699	-3.558	0.001
hemi-left+right	0.010	0.026	508.701	0.366	0.715
ConditionSign:groupHA	-0.121	0.146	57.199	-0.826	0.412
ConditionSilent:groupHA	-0.065	0.146	59.808	-0.445	0.658
ConditionSign:groupCI	0.274	0.124	57.39	2.219	0.030
ConditionSilent:groupCI	0.428	0.124	61.241	3.457	0.001
ConditionSign:hemi-left+right	0.031	0.037	508.701	0.834	0.405
ConditionSilent:hemi-left+right	0.046	0.037	508.701	1.240	0.216
groupHA:hemi-left+right	-0.020	0.059	508.701	-0.341	0.733
groupCI:hemi-left+right	0.042	0.050	508.701	0.835	0.404
ConditionSign:groupHA:hemi-left+right	0.060	0.084	508.701	0.723	0.470
ConditionSilent:groupHA:hemi-left+right	-0.003	0.084	508.701	-0.030	0.976
ConditionSign:groupCI:hemi-left+right	-0.039	0.071	508.701	-0.557	0.578
ConditionSilent:groupCI:hemi-left+right	-0.135	0.072	508.701	-1.884	0.060

The results of the third exploratory model did not reveal any significant effects involving Vocabulary scores. The fourth and final exploratory model detected a trending main effect of Sign language exposure, estimated at +0.093 μM , indicating a tendency towards larger auditory activation with at least some prior sign language exposure. There were also significant interactions of Sign language exposure and Condition (estimated at -0.136 μM and -0.152 μM , respectively, for the auditory vs sign and the auditory vs silent contrasts). Inspection of the estimated means and 95% confidence intervals revealed that CI children with at least some prior sign language exposure had a reliable activation to auditory speech (estimated mean = 0.173 μM , CI = 0.034–0.312 μM), while no reliable activation to auditory speech was detected for CI children without prior sign language exposure (estimated mean = -0.0131 μM , CI = -0.174–0.148 μM). The estimated means per Group

and Condition in interaction with Vocabulary scores are plotted in panel C of Fig. 6, and the means per Condition and Sign language exposure are plotted in panel D of Fig. 6.

4. Discussion

This study investigated auditory cortical activation in prelingually deaf and normal-hearing preschool and early school-age children across three conditions: auditory speech with restricted visual cues, silent speech, and sign language. The first goal was to assess activation to auditory and visual language stimuli (silent speech and sign language) in the temporal lobe regions across children with different hearing profiles: hearing-impaired children with cochlear implants (CI), hearing-impaired children with hearing aids (HA), and normal-hearing controls (NH). Secondly, in the hearing-impaired children, the study explored how hearing age, aided hearing thresholds, vocabulary score, and sign language exposure influence neural processing of auditory and visual language.

Hemodynamic activation in the left and right auditory cortices was measured using fNIRS. Changes in concentration of oxygenated hemoglobin (HbO) were taken as the index of cortical activation and analysed in a series of linear mixed-effects models.

4.1. Auditory speech processing across hearing-impaired and normal-hearing children

The analysis revealed that children with cochlear implants had weaker responses to auditory speech than children with normal hearing (while no difference was detected between children with hearing aids and children with normal hearing). Pairwise comparisons showed that CI children also had weaker auditory processing than HA children. This suggests that despite their compensation, CI children are still perceiving speech less efficiently than normal hearing children and also than children with hearing aids, who pattern more with NH children (but also note that sound level of auditory stimulation was 10 dB louder for the HA and CI children than for the NH children, as explained in the Methods section).

One potential explanation could lie in the differences in audiometry outcomes (PTA thresholds), which in general are worse (i.e. larger) in CI than in HA children. However, our exploratory analysis examining the effect of pure-tone audiometry did not detect the effect that would be

Fig. 4. Estimated means and 95% confidence intervals of HbO change across groups and conditions, in the left and right hemisphere.

Fig. 5. Modelled HbO values on all channels for each group and condition.

expected under the sound-level explanation. One might also argue that the difference between CI and HA children is due to their hearing age, which is typically lower for CI children than for HA children because CI children generally receive their compensation device at a later age than HA children. However, our exploratory analysis did not detect any effect of hearing age on the strength of auditory activation (which of course does not imply that such an effect does not exist).

Another potential explanation for the weaker auditory speech processing in CI children, and one which we consider very likely, could lie in the quality of auditory input that the children's brains receive through their devices. As for the quality of the auditory signal, in HA children, the speech signal is, in its full unmodulated form, amplified before entering the cochlea. In CI children, the auditory speech signal is transformed into a spectrally degraded electrical stimulation pattern that conveys only limited frequency and temporal detail to the auditory nerve. Lastly, the absence of lipreading cues in the auditory speech condition, which are known to enhance speech perception accuracy in children with hearing loss (Lalonde and McCreery, 2020), may have further contributed to less efficient processing in the hearing-impaired children. We suggest that future research should attempt to quantify the quality of experience with spoken language, as well as the degree of reliance on multimodal speech cues, and test whether and in what ways they affect speech processing in CI children (possibly in interaction with

other factors such as hearing age or aided audiometry).

4.2. Cross-modal activation for silent speech and sign language

Recall that previous studies with hearing-impaired children reported cross-modal activation to visual speech. For instance, using silent speech stimuli, Mushtaq et al. (2020) with 6–12-year-old children, and Zhou et al. (2023) with 6–8-year-olds, found greater activation of the temporal brain regions in CI children than in NH peers (both studies indicating adaptive effect of the identified cross-modal reorganisation). Although neuroimaging research on sign language processing in young children is lacking, studies with adults indicate that sign language stimuli yield stronger activation in the auditory cortex in hearing impaired subjects compared to NH participants (Petitto et al., 2000, Capek et al., 2010; Que et al. 2018).

Based on prior literature we expected to find cross-modal activation to visual language in hearing-impaired children because, compared to normal-hearing children, they had delayed access to spoken language. Specifically, we predicted that in children with CIs as well as in children with HAs, silent speech and sign language stimuli would yield activation in the auditory cortex.

However, our results support this prediction only to a limited extent. First, the activation to silent speech that we detected in children with

Fig. 6. Estimated HbO values per Condition and Group, means, 95% confidence intervals, and individual data points (each participant on channel 6 left and channel 6 right): (A) effect of Hearing age in HA and CI children, (B) effect of PTA thresholds in HA and CI children, (C) effect of Vocabulary core in HA and CI children, (D) effect of prior Sign language input in CI children (recall that “none” = children received no sign language input or only a few isolated signs, “some” = children received sign language input prior to implantation).

hearing loss was very limited, despite previous studies that reported this phenomenon in both adults and children. In the present experiment, reliable activation of the auditory cortex in response to silent speech was found only in children with cochlear implants and it was restricted to the left hemisphere. For sign language, our results failed to show cross-modal activation in either the CI or the HA children. Rather unexpectedly, there was a reliable cross-modal activation to sign language in normal-hearing children. The NH children's response to sign language was right-lateralized, occurring at the same channel at which the children also had strong response to auditory speech (with a similar, but nonsignificant, trend observed in the left hemisphere).

The cross-modal activation to sign language in NH children with no prior experience with sign language could be explained when one considers language rhythm. Right-hemisphere activation is associated with the processing of relatively large linguistic chunks, i.e. slow rhythms below ~4 Hz (Poeppl, 2003; Bourguignon et al., 2013). These encompass the temporal rhythms of sign language of about 1 Hz, which are reliably tracked by hearing adult non-signers (Brookshire et al., 2017; Rivolta et al., 2025). In line with that, we propose that the significant right-lateralized activation in the NH children reflects their ability to “tune in” to sign language at a rhythmic level. One may ask why such tuning in to sign language rhythms did not emerge in the children with hearing loss as well, particularly in CI children, many of whom were familiar with the visuospatial language modality. Potentially, in the mixed blocked design used in the present experiment,

focusing on and (automatically) tracking the somewhat iconic child-directed – yet unfamiliar – sign language, might have been an easier task for NH children than for the DHH children who had to exert comparably more effort in the auditory and silent speech trials. We like to argue that the present findings of cross-modal activation in normal hearing children can serve as strong evidence against the claims of a visual takeover theory that visual language input may hamper spoken language development. We believe our findings debunk this claim as we found activation to visual sign language stimuli in the auditory cortices of normal-hearing children, who, at the same time, in the same cortical region, exhibited also strong activation to auditory speech stimuli.

4.3. Cross-modal inhibition for silent speech

Despite not being modelled in the present study, we will now comment on the visual shape of the responses in the silent speech condition. Interestingly, in children with hearing aids, as well as in normal hearing children, on multiple channels the hemodynamic responses to silent speech were observed to have an inverted pattern, characterised by negative HbO and positive HbR values.

The interpretation of such an inverted HRF shape is not trivial, as the patterns we have observed are rather rarely reported and hardly ever systematically discussed in prior literature on language processing. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to observe an inverse hemodynamic response to visual silent speech in both normal-hearing

children and children with hearing aids. Given our predictions of cross-modal *activation* in the population of children with hearing loss, which, following prior studies, should be manifested as a positive HbO profile, identifying an inverted HBR shape is somewhat surprising. In the literature, an inverse HbO profile has been associated with the processing of unintelligible speech (compressed speech with newborns in [Issard and Gervain, 2017](#); speech in noise in CI adults in [Levin et al., 2022](#)) and with inhibitory processes in the measured region (e.g. visual speech in hearing adults' left auditory cortex in [Shader et al., 2021](#); visual speech in normal hearing children in [Mushtaq et al., 2020](#)).

Outside language, prior studies reported inverted hemodynamic responses in motor areas during motor imagery tasks, such as drawing, balancing while standing, and ball squeezing ([Kempny et al., 2016](#); [Almulla et al., 2022](#)). [Holper et al. \(2011\)](#) found a positive HbO response in complex motor execution task and a negative HbO response in complex motor imagery task, suggesting that an imagery task initiates inhibitory processes to actually suppress sensory inputs that might interfere with the goal of the imagery task at hand. To this end, there is evidence that visual stimuli can initiate verbal imagery following auditory priming ([Jäncke and Shah, 2004](#)). We propose an analogy between seeing a face with moving articulators and anticipating hearing the speaker's voice ([Pekkola et al., 2005](#)), especially if the speaker has been heard/seen before (as in our mixed-block design). As for the apparent lack of inverted responses in CI children, one might speculate that the absence of an inhibitory response in the CI children reflects their reduced audiovisual integration capability associated with shorter and more disrupted hearing experience. Some prior studies explain a reversed hemodynamic response in a specific cerebral area in terms of disengagement of the given area ([Deroche et al., 2024](#)), or as spatial redistribution of cerebral blood flow to other brain areas, a phenomenon known as "blood stealing" ([Shmuel et al., 2002](#); [Steinmetzger et al., 2020](#)). While blood or vascular stealing may appear as inhibition, it does not necessarily reflect changes in activation within the region of interest but instead hemodynamic activation in a different region that "steals" the oxygenated hemoglobin from regions not involved in processing.

In the present study, stimuli were always preceded by silent intertrial intervals with static simple cartoon images. Since the present HbO data are baselined to (portions of) these pre-stimulation silent intervals, it is unlikely that the inverted response to the – again silently presented – visual speech stimulus would have simply been due to a reduced excitability of the auditory cortex. Instead, it is likely that the silently presented visual speech stimulus actually elicited the inhibition. Such inhibition could be caused by auditory pathway suppression during visual speech imagery, or due to vascular stealing by other regions involved in the processing of the visual speech stimulus such as the visual cortex, or a combination of both the auditory suppression and the vascular stealing mechanism. The elicited inhibition turns out to be the most plausible explanation if one considers also the results for the CI children who did not show inverted responses in the silent speech condition. To test which of the above-discussed mechanisms causes the inverted response to visual speech in the auditory cortex, future research should replicate the present experiment with a whole-head fNIRS montage.

4.4. Factors that influence speech processing in hearing-impaired children

In addition to addressing cross-modal activation, we explored whether the cortical activation in children with hearing impairment is modulated by various audiometric and linguistic factors. To this end, we modelled the influence of (i) hearing experience, specifically its duration in terms of hearing age, (ii) hearing quality in terms of aided pure-tone average thresholds, (iii) spoken language competence in terms of vocabulary scores, and (iv) sign language experience in terms of sign language input prior to implantation. As for the audiometric factors, we failed to detect an effect of hearing age and detected an interaction effect of pure-tone aided audiometry, which rather counterintuitively

suggested stronger activation to auditory speech processing in children with worse hearing thresholds. We do not interpret this unexpected effect as it was found with a small sample ($n = 14$ across the CI and HA group) and leave it for further, hypothesis-driven, investigation in future research.

As for the linguistic factors, the model for vocabulary scores failed to detect any significant effects, but the model for sign language experience did yield an effect. Specifically, CI children who had at least some Czech Sign Language (CSL) exposure prior to implantation, had reliable hemodynamic responses to auditory speech, as opposed to CI children without systematic CSL input. The reliable response to auditory speech in CI children with prior sign language experience suggests that early sign language exposure may provide a scaffolding effect for the development of auditory language processing. While this hypothesis requires further investigation, the present findings contribute to the growing body of evidence highlighting the benefits of early exposure to sign language.

5. Conclusion

The present findings contribute to the understanding of language processing in hearing-impaired children. Children with cochlear implants exhibited weaker auditory speech processing than both normal-hearing children and children with hearing aids, likely explainable by qualitatively different hearing experience across the groups of hearing-impaired children.

Contrary to predictions, cross-modal activation of the auditory cortex was found, right-laterally, for visual sign language stimuli in normal-hearing children (and was not detected in the hearing-impaired children). We explain this effect in terms of right-lateralized processing of the slow linguistic rhythms in sign language. We argue that the cross-modal activation in normal-hearing children demonstrates that the activation of auditory cortex to both visual and auditory language stimuli is possible, providing further evidence against the visual takeover theory.

Inverted responses were observed for silent speech stimuli and were discussed as likely reflecting inhibitory activity associated with verbal imagery during lip reading. In children with cochlear implants prior experience with sign language experience was associated with enhanced processing of auditory speech, compared to cochlear-implanted children without sign language experience. This finding refutes some of the prior proposals that sign language input would hamper speech development after hearing restoration. The underlying mechanisms responsible for the inverted hemodynamic responses, as well as the modulating effects of sign language exposure in hearing-impaired children, merit further investigation.

Data availability statement

All data, materials, and analysis scripts associated with this study are available on the Open Science Framework (OSF) at the following link: <https://osf.io/yeg9j/>

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Michaela Svoboda: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization, Visualization. **Natálie Kikořová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization. **Monika Kučerová:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration. **Jakub Dršata:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration. **Jana Krtíčková:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration. **Viktor Chrobok:** Supervision. **Kateřina Chládková:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.neuroimage.2026.121835](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2026.121835).

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